

Dapatkan hadiah menarik:
sambil Instagram
mataaksara
kegiatan di Mata Aksara. Tandai
Mata Aksara dalam keterangan foto

WHERE WE WORK

In 2019, EIFL worked in partnership with library consortia in 38 countries and ran projects in an additional 15 countries where we do not have library consortia.

- **PARTNER COUNTRIES** are countries where we have a formal agreement with the national library consortium. EIFL partner consortia work with all EIFL programmes.
- **PROJECT COUNTRIES** are countries in which we work with libraries on specific projects.

WHERE WE WORK

EIFL works in collaboration with libraries in 53 developing and transition countries.

AFRICA Botswana, Democratic Republic of Congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Lesotho, Malawi, Namibia, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe **ASIA PACIFIC** Cambodia, China, Fiji, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Laos, Maldives, Mongolia, Myanmar, Nepal, Thailand, Uzbekistan **EUROPE** Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Estonia, Georgia, Hungary, Kosovo, Latvia, Lithuania, Macedonia, Moldova, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia, Ukraine **LATIN AMERICA** Chile, Colombia **MIDDLE EAST & NORTH AFRICA** Palestine, Sudan, Syria.

CONTENTS

WHERE WE WORK	2
DIRECTOR'S REPORT	3
EIFL AT A GLANCE 1999 – 2019	4
WHO WE ARE	5
CHANGING CHILDREN'S LIVES IN GHANA	7
MEET THE PEOPLE	10
FINANCIAL REPORT	18
EVENTS	19
OUR PARTNERS	21
OUR TEAM	22
STAY CONNECTED	23

DIRECTOR'S REPORT

This annual report celebrates EIFL's 20th anniversary – a very special event for many people who have been with us all these years, and who have helped to build and shape the organization.

In 2019 we celebrated EIFL's 20th anniversary – a very special event for the many people who have helped to build and shape the organization over all these years. To mark this important milestone, we have assembled 'EIFL at Glance 1999 – 2019' with the contributions that each of our programmes has made in removing barriers to accessing and sharing knowledge.

2019 saw the continuation of a global shift in negotiations with journal publishers. Starting from 2019, all EIFL's negotiations included not only free or discounted subscriptions to paywalled journals, but also discounts and waivers of Article Processing Charges (APCs), which are the fees authors pay to make their articles available in open access. As a result, authors from EIFL partner countries can now publish their articles in open access for free or at greatly reduced APCs in over 700 open access journals from four publishers. We expect these numbers to grow.

We are excited about a new project which started in October in Myanmar to establish a national open access repository that will collect, disseminate and preserve all research output from universities. The Myanmar Education, Research and Learning (MERAL) Portal project, in collaboration with the Department of Higher Education of the Ministry of Education, the Rectors' Committee, and the National Institute

of Informatics of Japan, builds on EIFL's significant support for open access in Myanmar since 2015.

In 2019, while we continued to advocate with governments to join the Marrakesh Treaty for print-disabled people, we co-organized the first workshop focusing on practical steps for libraries to take to make full use of their new rights under the treaty. And during the year, two more EIFL partner countries joined the treaty – Thailand and Zimbabwe.

In 2019 we also celebrated the 10th anniversary of the EIFL Public Library Innovation Programme (EIFL-PLIP). We are delighted to feature in this Annual Report the great results of an EIFL-PLIP supported project in Ghana which opened the doors to further education for thousands of junior high school children by helping them to pass their ICT exams and progress to secondary school.

Thank you to everyone, past and present – our partners and funders, our board members and our committed staff – who have helped to bring us closer to achieving our vision of a world in which all people have the knowledge they need to achieve their full potential.

– Rima Kuprytė, Director of EIFL

EIFL AT A GLANCE 1999 – 2019

EIFL has worked in 70 developing and transition economy countries. Here are some of the results of our work over 20 years.

AFFORDABLE ACCESS TO E-RESOURCES

EIFL's first activity was to negotiate with publishers for affordable access to e-resources, including journals, e-books and databases, and to provide these to libraries in developing and transition economy countries. By negotiating free and discounted access to e-resources, EIFL has saved our library partners millions of dollars annually.

To ensure that e-resources negotiated by EIFL reach the greatest number of people, we have helped libraries to organize themselves into national consortia that include all types of libraries – academic, research, national, specialised and public libraries. Over 20 years, we have conducted consortium building workshops in 68 countries, leading to the development of well functioning library consortia that manage the licensing of e-resources. We also work closely with library consortia to promote awareness of available e-resources, and to encourage subscriptions and usage. The e-resources have been very well used over the years.

- **120** products that include e-books, journals and databases negotiated
- **55** publishers signed agreements
- **80 million** downloads of full text articles and book chapters

OPEN ACCESS TO RESEARCH

EIFL was an original signatory to the Budapest Open Access Initiative declaration (2002), which coined the term 'open access' (OA), which is the immediate, free and online availability of research literature.

Since then, we have been an active player in the global open access movement. We have been advocating for open access to publications and data, raising awareness about open science and providing training. We participate in the EU-funded flagship project, OpenAIRE, which implements EU open science policies and set up a European infrastructure for open science, the OpenAIRE portal, a free and open discovery space for publications, data and software. In EIFL partner countries, we support the drafting of policies that mandate open access to research and have helped to set up infrastructure for open access content.

- **8** national open access policies
- **159** institutional open access policies
- **1,200** open access repositories
- **1,400** training events
- **262,000** librarians, researchers, policy-makers and open access champions trained

FAIR COPYRIGHT LAWS

We are engaged in national and international copyright law reform so that libraries can fulfill their public interest mission in providing equitable access to knowledge.

We obtained permanent observer status at the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). At WIPO we contributed to the development of a proposal for an international treaty on copyright exceptions for the benefit of libraries and archives, and strongly supported the adoption by member states of the Marrakesh Treaty for persons with print disabilities. This landmark treaty makes it possible for libraries, and other entities, to convert printed works into accessible formats and to exchange these works across national borders, opening the doors to knowledge and education for millions of print-disabled people.

- **14** countries drafted national copyright law revisions or adopted provisions that benefit libraries
- **18** countries ratified the Marrakesh Treaty – **20%** of all WIPO member states that have joined the treaty
- **143** resources created in **14** languages to support copyright advocacy and capacity building of librarians

COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT

EIFL has helped shift perceptions of public libraries and has inspired public librarians to innovate by providing small grants to implement new technology-based services, and through advocacy and training. The new library services improved people's health; helped unemployed people to get jobs; built community technology skills; connected farmers to new sources of information; helped children improve their marks at school, and more. Many of the projects we supported inspired replication by other public libraries globally.

Since 2017, our focus has been on Africa, where we advocate with governments to equip public libraries with digital technology, and build capacity of public librarians to introduce new library services that meet community information needs.

- **3** countries – Ghana, Kenya and Uganda – included public libraries in national ICT roll-out programmes
- **400** public libraries introduced innovative technology-based services in **27** countries on four continents
- **1,000** public librarians trained from **350** libraries that have computers and the internet in Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Namibia, Uganda and Zambia

WHO WE ARE

EIFL (Electronic Information for Libraries) is an international not-for-profit organization that works with libraries in developing and transition countries to enable access to knowledge for education, learning, research and sustainable community development.

THE CHALLENGE

Access to knowledge is fundamental to education and research. It can break the cycle of poverty, improve employability and health, and promote sustainable development.

However, billions of people in developing and transition economy countries cannot benefit from the new opportunities knowledge provides due to factors such as the high cost of e-resources, legal barriers to accessing and using information, and poor telecommunications infrastructure.

OUR VISION

A world in which every person has the knowledge they need to achieve their full potential.

OUR MISSION

EIFL enables access to knowledge through libraries in developing and transition economy countries to support sustainable development.

OUR VALUES

EIFL embraces the following core values:

- Practical, sustainable, local solutions
- Collaboration and partnership
- Knowledge sharing
- Innovative approaches

WHAT WE DO

- We build capacity by organizing training events, developing tools and resources, and providing up-to-date information on issues that affect access to knowledge.
- We advocate for access to knowledge nationally and internationally.
- We encourage knowledge sharing through peer-to-peer learning, best practice case studies, our annual conference, and cooperation between library consortia.
- We initiate pilot projects for innovative library services.

OUR APPROACH

EIFL works to expand access to knowledge in a cost effective and sustainable way by supporting the establishment and development of strong national library consortia.

Library consortia in 38 countries in Africa, Asia and Europe, representing almost 3,000 libraries, are part of the EIFL network.

OUR CORE INITIATIVES

- **Access to Knowledge for Education, Learning and Research** – ensuring well-resourced libraries, modern information and communications technology (ICT).
- **Access to Knowledge for Sustainable Livelihoods** – helping to transform people's lives through innovative services in public libraries.

OUR PROGRAMMES

Licensing Programme (EIFL-Licensing)
Negotiates affordable access to commercial e-resources, promotes awareness, and encourages usage.

Copyright and Libraries Programme (EIFL-IP) Advocates for national and international copyright law reform, and supports librarians to become advocates for a fair copyright system.

Open Access Programme (EIFL-OA)
Removes barriers to knowledge sharing by advocating for the adoption of open access (OA) policies and mandates, and by building the capacity to launch and sustain OA repositories and journals.

Public Library Innovation Programme (EIFL-PLIP) Advances community development by enabling public libraries to implement innovative ideas that use technology to improve people's lives and livelihoods.

**OUR VISION IS A WORLD IN
WHICH ALL PEOPLE HAVE THE
KNOWLEDGE THEY NEED TO
ACHIEVE THEIR FULL POTENTIAL.**

CHANGING CHILDREN'S LIVES IN
GHANA

EIFL and the Ghana Library Authority work together to bring ICT classes to under resourced schools

Excited children greet the mobile library.
Photo provided by Volta Regional Library.

“Every week, parents move their children from other schools, which are not benefitting from the mobile library project, to my school. They want their children to have this opportunity to learn about technology and pass their exams.”

– FRANCIS PEPRA BOANSI, HEADMASTER OF KWASO PRESBYTERIAN JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL IN ASHANTI REGION.

From 2015 to 2019 EIFL supported a mobile library project that helped over 3,200 children attending poor and rural schools in four regions of Ghana to pass the crucial Basic Education Certificate Exam, which determines progress to secondary school.

“The hands-on computer classes helped me pass the ICT exam!” Anna, the daughter of farmers in Ghana’s Volta Region, was one of thousands of children who passed the Basic Education Certificate Exam (B.E.C.E.) as a result of a project supported by EIFL.

Failing the B.E.C.E., which is the crucial exam that determines progress to secondary school, would have been devastating. “It would have been the end of my education. I would have just been at home because to repeat the exam is expensive,” said Anna.

ICT (Information and Communication Technology) is one of eight compulsory subjects in the B.E.C.E. However, many schools in poor and rural areas of Ghana do not have computers or internet connections. As a result, children learn ICT in the abstract. Without practical experience – sometimes without ever having seen or touched a computer – thousands of children fail every year, and are taken out of school by parents who cannot afford school uniforms and fees.

Librarians at Volta Regional Library, which is one of 10 regional libraries managed by the Ghana Library Authority (GhLA), came up with an innovative idea to improve the B.E.C.E. pass rate in their community. The regional library is based in the town of Ho, which is the administrative capital of Volta Region and the market centre for nearby

villages where families farm with livestock, fish, fruit and vegetables. Their idea was to equip a mobile library with low-power laptop computers, solar panels and modem internet, and to travel to under resourced junior high schools in Ho municipality to conduct hands-on computer classes. In 2012, the EIFL Public Library Innovation Programme (EIFL-PLIP) awarded Volta Regional Library a small grant for a year-long pilot project to test their idea in five schools.

“The ICT classes organized for us by the mobile library service contributed so much to my success in the B.E.C.E. I wish that they acquire more computers so that more juniors can get practice, and perform better in the exams,” said Zantor, a student at Ziavi Lume Methodist Junior High School in Volta Region.

FUNDRAISING TO EXPAND THE PROJECT

The pilot project was so successful that we launched a fundraising campaign for it through the online fundraising platform, GlobalGiving UK. In 2015 our campaign attracted major funding from the technology company, Nokia, enabling us to scale up the project to include mobile libraries in three more regions – Ashanti, Upper East and Western – with the potential to reach over 1,800 children in more than 20 schools annually.

Each of the three new regional libraries received 15 laptop computers and solar panels to charge them; a modem for the internet; a canopy, desks and chairs for large outdoor classes; a projector and

screen, and a printer to print out notes for the children to take home. We were also able to buy more computers and additional equipment for Volta Regional Library. Working with Accra-based social enterprise, TechAIDE, we installed the equipment in the mobile libraries. TechAIDE also preloaded the laptops with content related to school subjects, like geography, mathematics, science and English, e-books, as well as practice exam questions and other useful and fun learning tools.

The three libraries consulted with their regional education offices, and identified 15 under resourced schools (five in each region) that would receive classes. Librarians from the three regions visited Volta Regional Library to learn how to prepare their mobile libraries for the classes; how to use solar power; how to download software updates and troubleshoot technical problems, and to see the hands-on computer classes in action. We organized a joint workshop for librarians and ICT teachers from the 15 selected schools at which librarians from Volta Region conducted training in how to manage large ICT classes using a limited number of laptops, how to use the pre-loaded educational content, and shared insights into teaching children ICT.

“When I heard that my school was to be one of the selected ones, that gave us great joy. This project is going to improve ICT learning. It will ease the burden of our teachers, and for the children who are struggling to comprehend computers in the abstract,” said James Tenga, headmaster of Yakoti Junior High School in Upper East Region.

Celebrations marked the launch of the hands-on computer classes in the three new regions in November 2015.

THE BEGINNING OF AN INCREDIBLE JOURNEY

Over four years, from 2015 to 2019, the mobile libraries in Ashanti, Western, Volta and Upper East regions travelled thousands of kilometres, and conducted thousands of classes in 20 schools, reaching an average of 3,000 children a year – almost double the 1,800 they had planned to reach.

They visited each school an average of three times a month during school terms, conducting two practical computer skills classes during each visit. When classes fell behind schedule, schools asked libraries to continue the classes over weekends and during school holidays – and they did.

The librarians and teachers worked with students in grades 1, 2 and 3, but paid special attention to Grade 3, the year students sit for the B.E.C.E. In each class, three to four children – sometimes more – shared a laptop. Careful management was needed to ensure that everyone had a turn to use the keyboard and mouse and to go online.

Along the way, there were challenges. The roads were bumpy, rutted and occasionally flooded. Sometimes the mobile libraries broke down. Early in 2019, GhLA recalled all the vans for refurbishment.

“Some parents and schools offered to pay for the services of a taxi to bring the laptops and the internet. Sometimes the librarians used their own cars, or another library

vehicle. Some schools came to the library during free periods and over weekends so they would not miss classes when we couldn't come," said Yaa Agyemang Opare-Adu, Head of Programmes and Partnerships at the GhLA.

Often, electricity at the schools was not working, and so the librarians and teachers were thankful to have the solar panels. When internet connections were poor, the preloaded educational material came in handy. The librarians found different ways of using the laptops - for example, Volta Regional Library included 30-minute sessions in which children read aloud from the laptops to improve their English comprehension skills so that they would better understand the B.E.C.E. questions.

EXCITEMENT ABOUT THE EXAM RESULTS

Every year in June Grade 3 students sat for the B.E.C.E. This was a huge moment for the students - but also for EIFL and the regional libraries, because the exam results were also a test of the effectiveness of the hands-on computer classes. So every year, we joined the students in their anxious wait for exam results.

When they came, they were remarkable. Year on year, there was a dramatic increase in the pass rate in the ICT exam in the schools where the mobile libraries offered classes. In 2014/15, before the expanded project started, the average pass rate in the subject ICT at B.E.C.E. level in the selected schools was just 45%. In 2016, it increased to 65%; in 2017 to 81%; in 2018 it was 85% and in 2019 it was 84%.

"I can proudly say that in 2018 ICT was the subject with the highest grades in the B.E.C.E. The project has transformed the children to become computer literates!" said Veronica McCarthy, the Head Teacher at Aboadze Catholic Junior High School in Western Region.

"When we can practise, the examination becomes very easy because we always

remember what we practise! The library's classes have also helped us students to do online research - and to acquire more information about what we are taught in class," said Mary, a student from Western Region.

Cliff from Ashanti Region, achieved a Grade 1 pass for his ICT exam in 2018. He is now a student at Adu Gyamfi Senior High School, where he is concentrating on the subject General Science - his dream is to become a medical doctor. Cliff's family cannot afford a home computer, and the hands-on computer classes have had a great impact on his life. During the gap between basic school and secondary school, he was able to get a job at an internet café. "I could be productive in my holidays, help others - and earn some money," he said.

A NATION-WIDE SERVICE IS BORN

Evidence of the impact of the project, collected by the four regional libraries, and advocacy by GhLA, convinced the Ghana Investment Fund for Electronic Communications (GIFEC), a government agency, to equip the remaining six mobile regional libraries operated by the GhLA with laptop computers. GIFEC's support makes it possible for the GhLA to transform the project into a sustainable service that will be offered in 10 regions: the four regions that took part in the EIFL project - Ashanti, Upper East, Volta and Western - and six more, Brong-Ahafo, Central, Eastern, Greater Accra, Northern and Upper West. From early 2020, 10 ICT-equipped mobile libraries will go on the road.

"EIFL has helped to build the foundation for extension of practical computer skills classes in under resourced schools across our country. We could not have achieved this without you. Thank you!" said Hayford Siaw, Chief Executive Officer of the GhLA.

Thank you to the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation Global Libraries Program and our donors through GlobalGiving, for supporting our project.

HANDS-ON COMPUTER CLASSES PROJECT AT A GLANCE - 2015 - 2019

Children who passed ICT in the Basic Education Certificate Exam

MEET THE PEOPLE

Using knowledge to change their lives and the lives of others

NAMUTENYA HAMWAALWA

DEPUTY DIRECTOR, LIBRARY AND ARCHIVES SERVICE NAMIBIA

Public libraries in Namibia are being equipped with computers and the internet for public use. The shift has presented challenges for the Namibia Library and Archive Service (NLAS), which oversees the work of 65 public libraries and over 260 public librarians.

“Our librarians needed new skills to include technology-based information and training services,” said Namutenya Hamwaalwa, Deputy Director of NLAS.

EIFL and NLAS entered into a partnership to strengthen continuous professional development of public librarians in Namibia. In 2018/19 EIFL trained 17 librarians from the NLAS public library network to become trainers in developing modern library services that meet community information needs.

“I observed our new trainers practising with their colleagues and I can see a huge difference in their abilities. Before the training, they were too shy even to stand up in front of a group and speak. The training has built their confidence – they are conducting workshops, preparing handouts, organizing and facilitating discussions. They are strong, interactive trainers – they are different people!” said Namutenya.

The trainers have already trained 63 librarians from 44 public libraries in four workshops, on design thinking, communications, advocacy, project management and searching the internet.

In 2019: EIFL trained 50 public library trainers in Kenya, Namibia, Uganda and Zambia who are now training other librarians in their countries.

“Most of the time when we want to train our librarians we have to get somebody from outside – external trainers to capacitate our librarians. But with this programme we will have experts locally.”

– NAMUTENYA HAMWAALWA

INGA DAVIDONIENE

DIRECTOR, LITHUANIAN LIBRARY FOR THE BLIND LITHUANIA

The Marrakesh Treaty gives libraries the right to convert printed works into accessible formats (such as braille, audio, large print and digital accessible formats) for print-disabled people without having to ask permission from rightsholders, and to share these works across borders. By the end of 2019, 88 countries worldwide had joined the treaty.

In September, EIFL co-organized a workshop for a group of neighbouring countries – Belarus, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, and Russia – that have either completed or are advancing implementation of the Marrakesh Treaty into national law. The workshop focused on practical steps for libraries to take to make full use of their new rights under the treaty.

The Lithuanian Library for the Blind (LAB) hosted the workshop.

“There are 19,000 blind and visually impaired people in Lithuania and they request material in various languages, including Russian and Polish,” said Inga Davidoniene, Director of LAB.

“Since the workshop, we have requested and received 16 publications in accessible formats from Ksiaznica Podlaska library in Poland. We agreed metadata for cataloguing with their librarians, and the transfers were made using the online file transfer service Wetransfer. The workshop gave us the practical knowledge to do this,” said Inga.

In 2019: Thailand and Zimbabwe joined the Marrakesh Treaty, bringing the number of EIFL partner countries that have joined the Treaty to 16.

“The workshop helped to create a regional team with one goal – to fully implement the Marrakesh Treaty for the benefit of our users. Now we have a clear vision for the concrete steps to be taken to receive material that we need to serve our users.”

– INGA DAVIDONIENE

DAVID BUKENYA

DEPUTY UNIVERSITY LIBRARIAN UGANDA

David Bukenya, Deputy University Librarian at Uganda Christian University (UCU), is a passionate advocate for open access (OA) – the immediate, online, free and unrestricted availability of research literature. His university was the first in Uganda to adopt an OA policy. In 2016 the Consortium of Uganda University Libraries (CUUL) appointed David to be EIFL Country Coordinator. David's appointment coincided with a major project that EIFL was implementing with CUUL to increase availability and visibility of Ugandan research. The project included setting up OA repositories and drafting, discussing and adopting institutional OA policies.

"The project was very intense. We worked with 11 universities, each with a different institutional dynamic. All 11 universities now have well-functioning OA repositories that are registered with search engines, and research from our universities can be easily found on the internet. The number of documents in the repositories has quintupled, to over 23,000.

"Adoption of OA policies took longer. Nonetheless, by the end of 2019, five of the 11 universities had adopted policies. At the other six, policies are in the pipeline," said David.

CUUL is continuing to provide on-demand support for repository managers and administrators through an online Uganda Dspace User Group.

In 2019: 66 new open access repositories were launched in the EIFL network.

"The appearance of open access repositories has increased universities' self-awareness – they are now more aware of the quantity and quality of their research output."

– DAVID BUKENYA

TIN WIN YEE

LEADER, COPYRIGHT ADVOCACY FOR LIBRARIES MYANMAR

Tin Win Yee, Group Leader of the Myanmar Library Association (MLA) Legal Affairs Committee, and EIFL Copyright Coordinator in Myanmar, led library advocacy to ensure that Myanmar's new copyright law, adopted in May 2019, would enable the development of modern, effective library services.

The Copyright Law of 2019 is one of many new laws that are being introduced as the country shifts to democracy after more than 50 years of military rule. It replaces a law enacted over a century ago, in 1914.

"We have over 5,000 libraries in Myanmar. It was essential that the new law would include appropriate limitations and exceptions to give libraries the freedom we need to support research and education, especially national priorities such as distance education," said Tin Win Yee.

EIFL reviewed the new copyright law at the draft stages, made recommendations on library provisions, held discussions with the local library community and met with policy-makers in Myanmar.

In 2017, the MLA submitted suggestions – including EIFL's recommendations – to Parliament when the copyright bill was being debated.

"Our advocacy was successful. Our suggestions on library provisions were included in the new copyright law," said Tin Win Yee.

In 2019: EIFL engaged in copyright law reform in 20 countries in the EIFL network.

"The new copyright law supports the delivery of online education, the creation of electronic course packs for teaching, and the provision of document delivery services by libraries, good news for learning and research in Myanmar."

– TIN WIN YEE

DR CECILE COULIBALY

DEPUTY DIRECTOR IN CHARGE OF RESEARCH, UVCI CÔTE D'IVOIRE

Dr Cecile Coulibaly coordinates the national open access repository, which is hosted by the Université Virtuelle de Côte d'Ivoire (UVCI). The main mission of the university is to enhance e-learning and digital skills in all higher education institutions in the country. Cecile is also EIFL Country Coordinator for Côte d'Ivoire.

In 2016, UVCI was mandated by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research to set up a national open access repository, but collecting research output from universities and clearing copyright were challenges.

In 2019, EIFL delivered a series of workshops for librarians and university administrators in Côte d'Ivoire on copyright management and licensing, institutional and national open access policies, and how to collect, describe and make research openly available in the national repository.

"The EIFL workshops have sparked discussion among all public universities and created a space for collaborative development of institutional and national open access policies in Côte d'Ivoire.

"There are already over 17,500 publications openly available in the national repository. We are also upgrading repository software to enable us to provide more services to researchers and universities and next year we are planning to adopt a national open access policy," said Cecile.

In 2019: Two more EIFL partner countries, Ethiopia and Serbia, adopted national open access policies.

"We are now sharing our experience of developing a national open access policy and repository with other Francophone countries in Africa."

– DR CECILE COULIBALY

DR IMAD IBRIK

RESEARCH DIRECTOR, AN-NAJAH NATIONAL UNIVERSITY PALESTINE

In developing countries, budgets for research are low or non-existent. This makes it difficult for researchers to publish their articles in open access (OA) journals that have Article Processing Charges (APCs).

To support researchers from these countries, EIFL negotiates with publishers for free or discounted APCs.

"We want to publish in OA journals because this is the best way to share our research widely, but with the high price of APCs we cannot afford it," said Dr Imad Ibrik, Director of the Energy Research Centre at An-Najah National University.

"I chose to publish my article about solar power and electrification of rural areas in Palestine in the Taylor & Francis OA journal Cogent Engineering. But the APC was €1,000 – and that is a lot of money."

In 2019, EIFL and Taylor & Francis signed an agreement that enables researchers from 37 EIFL partner countries to publish with discounted or waived APCs in over 130 fully OA journals that cover a wide range of disciplines, including the sciences, social sciences and humanities.

"I was extremely happy to receive a 50% discount, and my article has been published," said Dr Ibrik.

"I know that my colleagues are now also applying for discounts," he added.

In 2019: Authors in EIFL partner countries can publish in open access with waived or discounted APCs in 745 journals as a result of EIFL-negotiated agreements with four publishers.

"The discounted Article Processing Charges are encouraging researchers to submit their articles to high quality open access journals where they could not otherwise afford to publish."

– DR IMAD IBRIK

Zagreb City Libraries in Croatia trains people living in homeless shelters to use computers and the internet to look for jobs online. Photo by Vlado Cvirn for EIFL.

FINANCIAL REPORT

EIFL INCOME AND EXPENDITURE 2019

INCOME	€	%
• Programme income	3,578,815	80.5%
• Participation fees	372,891	8.4%
• General Support	390,743	8.8%
• Sponsorship, interest and other income	102,098	2.3%
Total	4,444,547	

EXPENDITURE	€	%
• Programme delivery	1,011,555	86.9%
• Personnel & contracted expenses	111,880	9.6%
• Operating expenses	40,772	3.5%
Total	1,164,207	

**COMMITTED EXPENDITURE FOR
2020 TO 2023 PROGRAMME DELIVERY** 3,265,869

CONTINUITY RESERVE 314,375

OUR FUNDERS

We would like to thank the following organizations and individuals for their generous support for our work in 2019.

ORGANIZATIONS

- Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation
- European Commission Horizon 2020 Programme
- Faculty of Information, University of Toronto
- International Commission of Jurists and the Danish Institute for Human Rights in Joint Venture (ICJ/DIHR)
- Luxembourg Development Cooperation Agency (LuxDev)
- Open Society Foundations
- Spider, The Swedish Program for ICT in Developing Regions
- UNESCO

INDIVIDUALS

In 2019, we conducted a fundraising campaign through GlobalGiving. Our 'Hands-on computer classes for 1,800 Ghana children' campaign raised over \$880.

EVENTS

In 2019, EIFL organized, supported or took part in 113 events, workshops and conferences about issues that affect access to knowledge.

JANUARY

- Webinar: Persistent Identifiers (Online)
- Open Science Trainer Bootcamp (Debrecen, Hungary)
- OpenAIRE General Assembly (Debrecen, Hungary)
- Cascade training on Design Thinking, and Project Management for Kenyan public librarians (Meru, Kenya)
- Webinar: Ubiquity Press open repositories platform (Online)

FEBRUARY

- EIFL eLibrary Myanmar project meetings (Mawlamyine, Yangon and Yezin, Myanmar)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE for Greece (Online)
- Workshops on Design Thinking, and Project Management for Namibian public library trainers (Windhoek, Namibia)
- Workshop: Sustainable non-APC publishing models (Bielefeld, Germany)
- Webinar: Authentication and remote access to e-resources (Online)

MARCH

- Workshops on open access repositories (Morogoro, Tanzania)
- Cascade training on Performance and Outcome Evaluation, and Rethinking Library Spaces for Kenyan public librarians (Mombasa, Kenya)
- Workshop: Communications and Advocacy for Kenyan public library trainers (Mombasa, Kenya)
- Workshop: Institutional open access policies in Kenya (Nairobi, Kenya)

- Workshop: Strengthening open access repositories in Africa (Accra, Ghana)
- Mandalay University Law faculty training on e-resources (Mandalay, Myanmar)
- Webinar: DOI Serbia (Online)
- Workshops for library leaders at EIFL eLibrary Myanmar project partner universities (Yangon, Myanmar)
- Workshop: Training Ghanaian Open Science trainers (Kumasi, Ghana)
- Open Science Bootcamp (Berlin, Germany)
- Webinar: How transformative agreements will accelerate the transition to open access (Online)
- Webinar: Transparency of publication fees and the OpenAPC project (Online)
- Webinar: Open Science – Inspiring Cultural Change In Your Library (Online)
- Webinar: Legal issues in dealing with research data (Online)
- Meetings with the Department for Public Reading, Ministry of Culture of Tunisia (Tunis, Tunisia)
- Meeting of the International Network of Emerging Library Innovators – Middle East and North Africa (Tunis, Tunisia)

APRIL

- Meetings with the Addis Ababa Culture and Tourism Bureau (Addis Ababa, Ethiopia)
- WIPO Standing Committee on Copyright and Related Rights (38th Session) (Geneva, Switzerland)
- Open Science Bootcamp (Kaunas, Lithuania)

- Research Data Management training for PhDs (Kaunas, Lithuania)
- UKSG Annual Conference (Telford, UK)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE for Greece (Online)
- Conference: Electronic Information for Science and Progress (Vilnius, Lithuania)
- Open Science and Research Data Management Train-the-trainer Bootcamp (The Hague, Netherlands)
- Open Science Bootcamp (Belgrade, Serbia)

MAY

- Webinar: OpenAIRE for Greece (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE for Italy (Online)
- Webinar: Taylor & Francis APCs (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE for Slovakia (Online)
- 3rd AfLIA Conference & 5th African Library Summit (Nairobi, Kenya)
- Webinar: Open Access and the Humanities: A Train-the-Trainer Perspective (Online)
- Conference: 'Nation Building through Quality Research and Innovation' (Yangon, Myanmar)
- Workshop on OpenAIRE (Ghent, Belgium)
- Workshop: Training and Facilitation skills for public library trainers from Uganda and Zambia (Lusaka, Zambia)
- 4th Global ESAC Workshop – Transformative Agreements in Practice (Munich, Germany)
- Webinar: Open Knowledge Maps (Online)
- Workshop: Initiative for Young African Library Innovators 2019 (Aarhus, Denmark)

JUNE

- Conference: Next Library 2019 (Aarhus, Denmark)
- Webinar: SAGE APCs (Online)
- Workshop: OpenAIRE services and tools for EaPConnect project partners (Kyiv, Ukraine)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE for Greece (Online)
- Conference: Open Repositories 2019 (Hamburg, Germany)
- Webinar: Horizon2020 policy (Online)
- WIPO Regional Seminar for the African Group on Libraries, Archives, Museums and Educational & Research Institutions in the Field of Copyright (Nairobi, Kenya)
- Workshop: 'Effective Training' for library trainers (Mandalay, Yangon, Myanmar)
- Cascade training on Internet Searching and e-Resources for Kenyan public librarians (Nairobi, Kenya)
- Workshop: Performance and Outcome Evaluation, Advocacy and Communications for Namibian and Ugandan public library trainers (Windhoek, Namibia)

JULY

- Cascade training on ICT skills, Project Management, Advocacy and Communications for Zambian public librarians (Livingston, Zambia)

AUGUST

- Webinar: Digital Humanities (Online)
- EIFL General Assembly (Bishkek, Kyrgyzstan)
- IFLA World Library and Information Congress (Athens, Greece)
- Legal e-resources training for Myanmar librarians (Yangon, Myanmar)

- Cascade training on Project Management, Community Needs and Impact Assessment for Ugandan public librarians (Kampala, Uganda)
- Law faculty training in the use of e-resources and conducting Moot Courts (Yangon, Myanmar)

SEPTEMBER

- Webinar: Meet Coko – modern publishing technology and community (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE for Slovakia (Online)
- Cascade training on Design Thinking, and Project Management for Namibian public librarians (Windhoek, Namibia)
- Open Science Fair (Porto, Portugal)
- ‘Open Talks’: Latin America and the Caribbean regional event marking UNESCO’s International Day for Universal Access to Information (Toluca, Mexico)
- Conference: Building an Information Society – Resources and Technologies (Kyiv, Ukraine)
- Conference: PUBMET 2019 (Zadar, Croatia)
- Meetings on Open Science in Georgia (Tbilisi, Georgia)
- Cascade training on Advocacy and Communications for Kenyan public librarians (Kericho, Kenya)
- Webinar: How to get published with SAGE (Online)
- Workshops: Open Science policies, repositories and training (Yerevan, Armenia)
- Workshop: ‘The Marrakesh Treaty: Getting Started’ (Vilnius, Lithuania)

OCTOBER

- EU Copyright Transposition Bootcamp (Warsaw, Poland)
- OA2020 Summit of Chief Negotiators (Berlin, Germany)
- 9th UNICA Scholarly Communication Seminar (Vilnius, Lithuania)
- Conference: University Development in Myanmar (Naypyidaw, Myanmar)
- WIPO International Conference on Copyright Limitations and Exceptions for Libraries, Archives, Museums and Educational & Research Institutions (Geneva, Switzerland)
- International Coalition of Library Consortia (ICOLC) meeting (Luxembourg)
- Cascade training on Project Management, Community Needs and Impact Assessment for Ugandan public librarians (Jinja, Uganda)
- Cascade training on Advocacy and Communications for Namibian public librarians (Windhoek, Namibia)
- WIPO Standing Committee on Copyright and Related Rights (39th Session) (Geneva, Switzerland)
- Webinar: Research Data Management (Online)
- Webinar: OpenAPC – cost transparency of open access publishing (Online)
- Workshops: Open access repositories and policies (Dakar, Senegal)
- Webinar: Horizon 2020 Open Science Policies (Online)
- Cascade training on Performance and Outcomes Evaluation for Namibian public librarians (Windhoek, Namibia)

- Workshop: Open access, and Open Science (Bishkek, Kyrgyzstan)
- International Symposium: Open Science in the South (Dakar, Senegal)
- Webinar: From Open Science to Inclusive Science (Online)
- Webinar: Plan S compliance for open access journals (Online)
- Cascade training on ICT skills, Project Management, Advocacy and Communications for Zambian public librarians (Lusaka, Zambia)
- Webinar: Janeway publishing platform (Online)

NOVEMBER

- Cascade training on ICT skills, Internet Searching and e-Resources, Project Management & New Service Development for Zambian public librarians (Kitwe, Zambia)
- Webinar: How to talk to faculty about open access (Online)
- Webinar: Google Scholar Indexing for OJS (Online)
- Workshops for public library trainers from Namibia and Uganda on Developing ICT training courses for library users, and Rethinking Library Spaces (Windhoek, Namibia)
- Webinar: Ask Me Anything About DSpace (Online)
- Workshops: Open Access Week (Abidjan and Bouaké, Côte D’Ivoire)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE Graph (Online)

- Workshop: How to conduct mobile public library ICT classes in under-resourced schools in Ghana (Accra, Ghana)
- Workshop: Training Open Science Trainers (Lviv, Ukraine)
- Internet Governance Forum (IGF) 2019 (Berlin, Germany)
- Webinar: URKUND plagiarism detection software (Online)
- Webinar: Open Science and Research Results Exploitation: Friends or Foes? (Online)

DECEMBER

- OpenAIRE General Assembly (Paris, France)
- Webinar: Library services to support measuring research impact (Online)
- Webinar: Phenom publishing platform (Online)
- MERAL Portal discussions (Yangon and Mandalay, Myanmar)
- Webinar: OpenAIRE Graph (Online)

KEY

- Training, workshops and events organized and/or supported by EIFL
- Presentations given by EIFL staff or partners
- Conferences and events attended by EIFL staff

OUR PARTNERS

EIFL has built relationships with a wide range of organizations to make knowledge more accessible. In 2019, we worked with the following partners:

- Access Now
- Addis Ababa Culture and Tourism Bureau, Ethiopia
- African Library and Information Associations and Institutions (AfLIA)
- American University of Central Asia
- Arab Federation of Libraries and Information (AFLI)
- Arab States Research and Education Network (ASREN)
- Association for Progressive Communicators (APC)
- Association of European Research Libraries (LIBER)
- Bioline International
- Bookshare
- British Council – Myanmar
- Centre for Internet and Society (India)
- Citizen's Services & Libraries, City of Aarhus, Denmark
- Coko Foundation
- COMMUNIA
- Confederation of Open Access Repositories (COAR)
- Copyright for Creativity
- Corporación Innovarte
- DAISY Consortium
- Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ)
- DSpace Community Advisory Team (DCAT), DuraSpace
- Education International
- Fundación Karisma
- GÉANT
- Gigabit Library Network (GLN)
- Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services (SCOSS)
- Google Scholar
- Harvard Open Access Project (HOAP)
- HIFA2020: Healthcare Information For All by 2020
- IEEE
- International Coalition of Library Consortia (ICOLC)
- International Council of Museums (ICOM)
- International Council on Archives (ICA)
- International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA)
- Internet Society
- Knowledge Ecology International (KEI)
- Libraries Development for the Local Government Management Agency in Ireland
- Lithuanian Library for the Blind
- Library Copyright Alliance (LCA)
- Maendeleo Foundation
- MentorNations
- Namibia Library and Archives Service
- National Institute of Informatics of Japan
- National Library of Uganda
- Networked Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (NDLTD)
- ORCID
- OA2020
- People Centered Internet (PCI)
- Program on Information Justice and Intellectual Property (PIJIP)
- Public Library Association (PLA) – American Library Association
- Public Knowledge Project (PKP)
- Rectors' Committee, National Education Policy Commission, Ministry of Education of Myanmar
- Right to Research Coalition
- SPARC
- SPARC Europe
- Tactical Tech
- Technology & Social Change Group (TASCHA), University of Washington
- Ubiquity Press
- UbuntuNet Alliance
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) in Asia and the Pacific
- University College Dublin
- UNESCO
- West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN)
- Wikimedia Deutschland
- World Blind Union (WBU)
- World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO)

KEY

- EIFL is a founding member/signatory
- EIFL is a member
- EIFL staff are board or committee members
- Official relations (including MoU)
- Working relationship

In addition, EIFL collaborated with 83 partners through European Commission-funded projects: Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE), FOSTER Plus (Fostering the practical implementation of Open Science in Horizon 2020 and beyond), Research Output Management through OA Institutional Repositories in Palestinian Higher Education (ROMOR), and Strengthening Research Management and Open Science Capacities of HEIs in Moldova and Armenia (Minerva).

OUR TEAM

Meeting of the EIFL network during the General Assembly held in Bishkek, Kyrgyzstan, from 8 – 10 August 2019.

STAFF

Andrius Kriščiūnas, Finance Manager
Aung Kyaw Soe, eLibrary Myanmar Project Coordinator for Mandalay
Edvaldas Baltrūnas, Public Library Innovation Programme Coordinator
Gwen Franck, Open Access Programme Coordinator
Iryna Kuchma, Open Access Programme Manager
Jean Fairbairn, Communications Manager, Website and Publications
Jevgenija Ševcova, Programmes and Events Coordinator
Louise Stoddard, Communications Manager (from June 2019)
Myat Sann Nyein, eLibrary Myanmar Project Coordinator for Yangon

Ramunė Petuchovaitė, Public Library Innovation Programme Manager
Rima Kuprytė, Director
Romy Beard, Licensing Programme Manager
Ruth Bird, eLibrary Myanmar Project Capacity Building Manager
Susan Schnuer, Public Library Innovation Programme Capacity Building Manager
Teresa Hackett, Copyright and Libraries Programme Manager
Tin Win Yee, eLibrary Myanmar Project Coordinator for Mawlamyine University (until June 2019)
Ugnė Lipeikaitė, Public Library Innovation Programme Impact Manager

MANAGEMENT BOARD

Arnold Hirshon, Chairperson, Kelvin Smith Library, Case Western Reserve University, USA
Emilija Banionytė, Vilnius County Adomas Mickevičius Public Library, Lithuania
Jyldyz Bekbalaeva, American University of Central Asia, Kyrgyzstan
Joel Sam, African Library and Information Associations and Institutions (AfLIA), Ghana
Winston Tabb, The Sheridan Libraries, The John Hopkins University, USA

NETWORK

We would like to thank all 100 EIFL Country Coordinators, Licensing Coordinators, Open Access Coordinators and Copyright Coordinators for their enthusiasm and hard work in 2019.

STAY CONNECTED

FACEBOOK: facebook.com/eifl.net

TWITTER: twitter.com/eiflnet

LINKEDIN: linkedin.com/company/eifl-net

FLICKR: flickr.com/photos/eifl/albums

YOUTUBE: youtube.com/user/eiflnet

eifl 2019
ANNUAL
REPORT

GET IN TOUCH

Mail: Mindaugo str. 23, LT-03214 Vilnius, Lithuania

Tel: +370 5 2080409 **Email:** info@eifl.net

For more information about EIFL and our work visit eifl.net